

DOES TRADE LIBERALIZATION CAUSE ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The activity of economic development has a negative impact on the quality of the environment, mostly as a consequence of production that involves the excessive use of natural resources and the residue that is produced as a result of this. The expansion of international commerce has a multiplicative effect on the environmental damage that is being experienced. In Uzbekistan, the purpose of this research is to investigate the impact that trade liberalization (TL) has had on environmental quality and to determine whether or not an environmental Kuznets curve (EKC) exists. By using the error correction model to yearly data spanning the years 1992-2021, this research also analyzes the dynamic link between the economic factors and the environmental variables using three equations: linear, quadratic, and cubic. All equations, with the exception of the linear equation, statistically show the influence of TL on the environment over the long term, according to the findings of this research. Furthermore, the EKC hypothesis is proven to be correct for all equations. In the short term, the CO₂ emission is somewhat controlled by TL in all kinds of equations, and the quadratic equation is responsible for the effect on the per capita annual income.*

Keywords: EKC, Income, Trade Liberalization

1. INTRODUCTION

The degradation of the environment is a direct result of economic growth that is largely sustained by natural resources and that ignores the principles of sustainability. In the future, economic growth will face challenges as a result of the limited carrying capacity of natural assets and the environment, as well as the lack of attention paid to these issues.

It would be interesting to analyze the link between economic development, trade, and environmental deterioration (the rise in CO₂ emissions) in a number of different economic fields. When it comes to that, at the very least, there are two primary concerns that need to be explored, among other things: First, the pattern of rising carbon emissions, which is in accordance with the agenda of the Kyoto convention, which places an emphasis on the need of short-term environmental measures to limit emissions of this kind. Regarding this matter, having a comprehension of the connection that exists between carbon dioxide emissions and gross domestic product (GDP) is of utmost significance as an input for the development of efficient public policy. Two, the liberalization of commerce, which boosts economic expansion but also contributes to a rise in pollution. According to Huang and Labys (2001), trade openness leads to a rise in the amount of international commerce, as well as an increase in foreign demand, economic development, and environmental damage.

Figure 1. The Relationship between economic growth and environmental degradation

Source: Everett et al. (2010, p. 20)

As a result of the fact that the issue of environment was on the agenda at the United Nations (UN) Conference on the Environment in Stockholm, Sweden in 1972, and continued with the UN conference on the environment in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil in 1992, which preceded the United Nations conference on climate change in Montreal, Canada in 1990, the trade-off between economic growth and environmental degradation became an interesting issue that was discussed. During the meeting, there were several individuals who said that the human population views environmental issues as a shared challenge, which necessitates the collaborative management of these issues by nations all over the globe. An extensive number of studies have been carried out in order to investigate the impact that economic development and trade liberalization (TL) have had on the quality of the environment in certain nations. The purpose of this research is to investigate the connection between economic growth and the deterioration of the environment, which is exemplified by the amount of carbon dioxide emissions seen in Uzbekistan. In order to illustrate the effect of the independent variables on the quality of the environment, both in the short term and over the long term, this research makes use of a dynamic econometric model, which is an Engle-Granger (EG) two step technique of error correction model (ECM).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are many different dimensions and complexities involved in the link between economic activity and the environment. The following is a beginning point explanation of how the link between economic activities and environmental interactions works, despite the fact that it may still be difficult to collect compelling proof of the form of economic activities and environmental relationships at the empirical level. It has been described by Everett et al. (2010) that, in general, the expansion of the economy has three consequences on the environment (Figure 1). Economic expansion has a detrimental impact on the environment, since the rise in production and consumption leads to an increase in the deterioration of the environment. To begin, the impacts of economies of scale are a significant contributor to this negative impact. Second, the effect of the composition, which is the composition of production along the growth path, which initially leads to industrialization (and the shift from agriculture to industries that cause the increase in the degradation of the environment), and then shifted the equilibrium of producing manufactured goods into an equilibrium of producing services. Thirdly, the technical effect: technology advancements lead to changes in the environmental impact of production. For instance, increases in energy efficiency might potentially be reflected by technological advancements that predict greater environmental harm. This is the third and final consequence.

Figure 2. Environmental Kuznets curve

Source: Everett et al. (2010, p. 17)

This is the link that the EKC hypothesis describes between the deterioration of the environment and the expansion of the economy. Everett et al. (2010) performed the first research that explore EKC. These investigations provided an analysis of the link between environmental degradation and income per capita. There is a long-term link between economic development and

environmental quality, and Grossman and Krueger discover that this relationship takes the form of an inverted U-shaped curve (Figure 2).

Panayotou (1993) calls this phenomena the environmental Kuznets curve (EKC), which is an acronym for the phrase. According to the following explanation, the Kuznets inverted U curve is as follows: To begin, the occurrence of a change in the transition of the agricultural sector into the manufacturing sector as a result of the promotion of foreign investment. Second, when the level of wealth rises, there will be a corresponding increase in the demand for environmental quality. When money is still low, it is difficult for governments in developing countries to make decisions that safeguard the environment. This is where it becomes challenging. People are able to begin paying for environmental damages that are the consequence of economic activity when their income begins to increase during this time period. According to Andreoni and Levinson (2001), at this point in time, individuals are prepared to forego the consumption of products in order to take steps toward protecting the environment.

When it comes to selecting the most appropriate indicator to employ in estimating the level of environmental deterioration, there are no clear norms from the past research. Among the researchers who make use of carbon dioxide emissions are Holtz-Eakin and Selden (1995), Roberts and Grimes (1997), and Moomaw and Unruh (1997). Grossman and Krueger (1991) found that other studies use fluctuating sulphur dioxide emissions to quantify the deterioration of the ecosystem.

The first theoretical contributions on literature of commerce and environment utilizing the ideal competitive model of the classical theory of trade. These contributions were made by Baumol. The emissions are included into the Heckscher-Ohlin trade model or the Ricardian framework in a number of studies, which are considered to be examples of models that are implemented. An example that is representative of this is the conventional model of the Heckscher-Ohlin equation, which includes certain commodities and pollution variables that are treated as extra production factors.

According to Baumol and Oates (1988), the economic theory presents evidence that the liberalization of commerce between nations that have varying levels of environmental protection may lead to the concentration of industries that produce a significant amount of pollution in nations that have less stringent environmental regulations. This impact is referred to as the pollution haven effect, and it is the most contentious issue of contention when it comes to the themes of TL and the environment. When it comes to the question of whether or not the pollution haven effect exists, the economic literatures are no closer to reaching an agreement. According to Copeland and Taylor (1994), if a nation internalizes the social cost of the environment and the environment does not include in commerce between countries, then the country that internalizes the social cost of the environment provides a competitive advantage of trade in goods that have significant environmental costs.

According to the results of both the short-term and the long-term assessments of the environmental influence on the trade model, less developed countries may choose to specialize in pollution-intensive commodities in order to prepare themselves for economic growth (Baumol, 1971; Baumol and Oates, 1988). This study was conducted by Baumol and Oates.

Because of the fact that efforts to distort trade pollution on likely spillover effects that may aggravate the other distortion, it is required to adjust the policies in a comprehensive way (Copeland and Taylor, 1994). This is because of the fact that the other distortion becomes worse.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this research, the dynamic econometric model, also known as the EG technique of ECM, is used to conduct an analysis of the dynamics of the short-run influence that independent variables have on the variable that is being studied.

Within the scope of this investigation, the EKC hypothesis was used to estimate three regression equations, which are as follows:

$$\text{Linear: } Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_r X_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Quadratic: } Y_t = \beta_2 + \beta_5 X_t + \beta_4 (X_t)_2 + \beta_5 TL_t + \varepsilon_{2t} \quad (2)$$

Cubic: $Y_t = \beta_6 + \beta_T X_t + \beta_s(X)_2 + \beta_g(X)_3 + \beta_{10} TL_t + \varepsilon_{3t}$ (3)

Where, Y_t is CO₂ gas emissions in year t (in kg/ton); X_{it} is real GDP per capita in year t (in US\$), as an indicator of the performance of economic development in a given year t ; TL_t is the TL in year t , i.e. the percentage of exports to GDP (in percent); β_0 is a constant; $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_{10}$, is the regression coefficient and ε_{it} is the error term for each equation i in year t .

It is possible to estimate the long-run equilibrium connection by simply calculating the regression of all of the variables that are cointegrated (Thomas, 1997). A long-term connection or equilibrium exists between two or more time series variables when they are cointegrated. This suggests that there is a relationship between these variables. Following the establishment of a time series connection that is both long run and mutually cointegrated, it is also possible to estimate the short-run disequilibrium that exists in the relationship between variables. Using Equation 3, the following is a concise explanation of how ECM models are derived; Equation 1 and Equation 2 are given using a process that is quite similar:

Estimation of Equation 3 need to be reordered. First, add the lag of independent variables, then reorder the equation with reduced Y_{t-1} on both sides:

$$Y_t - Y_{t-1} = b_0 + b_t X_t + b_2 X_{t-1} + b_3 (X)^2 + b_f (X_{t-1})^2 + b_s (X)^3 + b_6 (X_{t-1})^3 + b_7 T L_t + b_s T L_{t-1} + \mu Y_{t-1} - Y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

Perform addition and subtraction on the right side with:

$$b_7 X_{t-1}, b_3 (X_{t-1})^2, b_s (X_{t-1})^3, b_7 T L_{t-1}, \text{ then}$$

$$Y_t - Y_{t-1} = b_t + b_1 X_{t-1} - b_1 X_{t-1} + b_1 X_{t-1} + b_2 X_{t-1} + b_s (X_{t-1}) - b_s (X_{t-1})^2 + b_t (X_{t-1})^2 + b_s (X_{t-1})^3 - b_s (X_{t-1})^3 + b_s (X_{t-1})^3 + b_b (X_{t-1})^3 + b_1 T L_t - b_1 T L_{t-1} + b_7 T L_{t-1} + b_s T L_{t-1} - (1 - \mu) Y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (5)$$

and can be written also as

$$\Delta Y_t = b_0 + b_t \Delta X_t + (b_1 + b_2) X_{t-1} + b_3 \Delta (X_t)^2 + (b_3 + b_f) (X_{t-1})^2 + b_s \Delta (X_t)^3 + (b_s + b_t^2) (X_{t-1}^3) + b^3 \Delta T L_t + (b, + b)^3 T L_{t-1} - \lambda Y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

Where $\lambda = 1 - \mu$

From the above equation can be manipulated to form a new parameter, $\phi = \frac{b_1+b_2}{\lambda}, \phi_2 = \frac{b_3+b_4}{\lambda}, \phi_3 = \frac{b_5+b_6}{\lambda}, \phi_4 = \frac{b_7+b_8}{\lambda}$, namely so as

$$\Delta Y_t = b_0 + b_1 \Delta X_t + b_3 \Delta (X_t)^2 + b_5 \Delta (X_{t=1})^2 + b_7 \Delta (X_t)^3 - \lambda (Y_{t=1} - \alpha_0 - \phi_1 X_{t=1} - \phi_2 (X_{t=1})^2 - \phi_3 (X_{t=1})^3 - \phi_4 T L_{t=1}) + \varepsilon_t \quad (6)$$

Where, α_0 is a long-run constant of the model. Equation 11 can be referred to a first order modest ECM equation with $(Y_{t-1} - \alpha_0 - \phi_t X_{t-1} - \phi_2 (X_{t-1})^2 - \phi_3 (X_{t-1})^3 - \phi_t T L_{t-1})$ as an error correction term.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

In the first step of the study, an estimation of the EKC model over the long run is performed. Using linear, quadratic, and cubic equations, the findings of the long run model for the estimate of the EKC hypothesis are shown in Table 1. The diagnostic check has been performed on each and every regression model in order to accomplish the generation of the robust estimate. While the variable TL has not been shown to have any significant impact on the deterioration of the environment in Uzbekistan, the findings of the linear equation estimate reveal that the per capita income has a considerable negative impact on the degradation of the environment. When it comes to quadratic equations, the per capita income variable has a considerable negative influence on CO₂ emissions, but the TL variable has a favorable effect. It has been shown that the TL has a considerable favorable influence on CO₂ emissions, although the per capita income has not had such an effect, according to the cubic equation. According to the findings of the EKC model, it is claimed that an increase in the growth of per capita income generally has a negative effect on the environment. This implies that an increase in per capita income results in a decrease in CO₂

emissions, whereas an increase in low income per capita CO₂ emissions results in an increase in environmental degradation. It is possible for the model using the quadratic model to demonstrate an inverted U-shaped EKC hypothesis for Uzbekistan throughout the course of a lengthy period of time.

Table 1. Estimation result of long run EKC model

Variables	Coefficients and (t-stats)		
	Linear form	Quadratic form	Cubic form
Constants	245654.2	-54567.36	-74569.79
	(-3.35496)*	(-2.454089)	(-1.181874)
X	297.6807	33.43216	112.5489
	(23.76765)*	(0.645443)	(0.452678)
X ²	-	0.456354	0.112484
	-	(4.56552)*	(0.25882825)
X ³	-	-	2.51E – 05
	-	-	0.363383
TL	201.6915	1154.780	1335.791
	(0.374006)	(2.419442)*	(2.746487)*
R ²	0.899689	0.889020	0.899136
Adjusted R ²	0.876969	0.846438	0.875609
F -statistics	369.2123	389.34582	294.7553

*Significant at $\alpha = 1\%$.

Through the use of the EG test, cointegration has been applied to each equation in order to provide an explanation for the long-term connection or equilibrium that exists between the independent variables and the deterioration of the environment. The findings of the research indicate that all of the equations have cointegrated, as determined by the results of the cointegration.

Table 2: Estimation result of short run EKC model

Variables	Coefficients and (t-stats)		
	Linear form	Quadratic form	Cubic form
Constants	7356.209	7546.077	6589.424
X ₁	12569.8915 (1.749757)	-365.9126 (-1.451327)	9.745829 (0.014293)

X ₂	-	0.256990 (2.2431237)**	-0.478355 (-0.145320)
X ₃	-	- -	8.75E – 05 (0.4567356)
TL	-88.04664 (-0.172902)	156.8036 (0.349433)	145.9901 (0.274038)
Res1 (-1)	-0.347241 (-2.419037)**	-0.546632 (-3.698212)*	-0.740676 (-3.4846640)*
R ²	0.267026	0.499690	0.478197
Adjusted R ²	0.075628	0.402595	0.3694227
F-stat	2.3348775	6.3694180	5.356635

* Significant at $\alpha = 1\%$; ** significant at $\alpha = 5\%$.

The short run EKC model is the basis of the second set of estimates. The regression estimates are reported in Table 2, which can be seen here. Based on the findings, it is clear that the quadratic model is the only one that is capable of demonstrating the large influence that the per capita income has on CO₂ emissions. In contrast, the other models show that both the per capita income and the TL have little effect on CO₂ emissions. In all of the short run models, the ECT coefficient reveals that the difference between long-term and short-term CO₂ emissions is compensated by the size of the ECT coefficient in one period. This may be explained by the fact that the ECT coefficient is negative and substantial.

5. CONCLUSION

For the purpose of determining the nature of the long-term link between TL and the variable quality of the environment in Uzbekistan, this research makes use of a collection of static econometric models and a cointegration test. Additionally, the existence of EKC was shown to be true by this model. Using ECM, this research also investigated how the dynamic link between TL and income per capita is related to the quality of the environment in the near run. In the long run model, there is empirical evidence that TL has an influence on environmental degradation; but, in the short run, there is no evidence that the effect exists. In the sort run, there is no evidence that the effect exists. The EKC hypothesis, on the other hand, is only supported by quadratic models, and it is only in long-term models that it is possible to demonstrate the existence of the relationship between income per capita and environmental quality.

The considerable influence that TL has had on the quality of the environment in Uzbekistan over the course of extended periods of time suggests that environmental and economic policies have been integrated in order to reduce the adverse effects that trades have had on the environment. It is possible to demonstrate that the EKC theory had an effect on Uzbekistan. A rise in the average income of the population will lead to an increase in the rate of environmental deterioration. However, as the Uzbekistann economy reaches a turning point, there will be a reduction in the impact of environmental deterioration.

It is possible that this research has certain limitations, such as the availability of data over a lengthy period of time. The scope of this model will be expanded to include more factors that provide explanations, and it is necessary to do further in-depth research on the effects that the TL has on the environment.

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